

Effectiveness of Economic Empowerment of Coastal Communities Based On Local Potential In Selayar Regency, South Sulawesi, Indonesia

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Abstract:- Qualitative research through the Phenomenology Approach, the results of the study show that the potential of coastal communities needs attention, because the community that occupies the coastal areas of the majority of fishermen is one of the providers of primary needs, namely fishery products and marine products that are needed by people both living in the countryside and in cities, activities, their existence needs attention in the form of economic assistance, capital and education so that they are more skilled in managing natural resources professionally and maintaining the surrounding environment.

Keywords:- Coastal, economic, policy, capital, service,

I. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia's physical potential consisting of 17,508 islands and a coastline of 81,000 km, this condition means that Indonesia also has a very large coastal area. Coastal area is an area that is around the coast towards the sea and towards land. Coastal ecosystems include beaches, river estuaries, coral reefs, mangrove forests, coastal swamp forests, and waters near the coast (inshore). An area of more than 2/3 is the sea or reaches 5.8 million km² (580 million ha), Indonesia has a huge and diverse marine and fisheries potential both renewable and non-renewable, which is in the form of potential areas, natural resources, and marine services. The life of coastal communities is different from aspects of life in agrarian communities (residents who live in rural areas in general). This is due to natural environmental factors, because coastal communities are more associated with the dominant sea, while agrarian communities by natural environment in the form of rice fields, moors or fields. With these different conditions, it allows them to have different cultures and knowledge systems in meeting their daily needs. People who live in coastal areas are generally dependent on marine or coastal resources, so most of the population has a basic livelihood as fishermen. Apart from being a fisherman, some of its inhabitants also cultivate their land as ponds.

fish. This shows that marine resources have an important role for the lives of coastal communities. Selayar Regency is one of the regions in South Sulawesi that has enormous potential in the field of marine and fisheries. In

addition to the diverse catches of its kind, coral ecosystems and beauty.

The beach became the object of world-scale tourism. However, various problems that are currently experienced are the tendency to decrease the number of catches as a result of the decline in the quality of coral reef ecosystems, even estimated to be still good less than 20% (Coremap, 2010). The destruction of coral reef ecosystems is mostly caused by human activities, either directly or indirectly. For this reason, it is very important to know the activities carried out by coastal communities. One of the efforts in the management and protection of marine resources is to set aside locations that have the potential for plant and wildlife diversity, natural symptoms and uniqueness, and ecosystems into marine conservation areas. Through this way, it is hoped that efforts to protect the life support system, preservation of nutfah plasma sources and their ecosystems and the sustainable use of natural resources can be realized. Conservation efforts through the Aquatic Conservation Area are expected to minimize and prevent more severe loss of marine resources, namely by setting aside locations that have the potential for diversity of animal and plant species, uniqueness and natural symptoms, and ecosystems into several zones, namely core zones (no-take areas), sustainable fisheries zones, utilization zones and other zones, in addition to protecting the remaining resources, It also provides an opportunity for ecosystems to recover from damage.

Marine and fisheries resources are one of the natural wealth owned by Indonesia and widely utilized by the community. However, until now, the use of natural resources is less concerned about its sustainability, resulting in a decrease in quality and biodiversity.

exist. One of the tools for managing coastal and marine resources and has become a government policy is to develop a Water Conservation Area (KKP), namely by allocating some coastal and marine areas as a shelter for economically important fish to colonize and breed properly. By allocating some coastal and marine areas that have high biodiversity, healthy ecosystems, and providing shelter for fish resources, it will eventually support fisheries and tourism activities sustainable.. Conservation efforts through the Aquatic Conservation Area are expected to minimize and prevent more severe loss of marine resources, namely

by setting aside locations that have the potential for diversity of animal and plant species, uniqueness and natural symptoms, and ecosystems into several zones, namely core zones (no-go areas), sustainable fisheries zones, utilization zones and other zones (PP No.60 / Year 2007). This effort, in addition to protecting the remaining resources, also provides an opportunity for the eco-system to recover from damage. Conservation is the responsibility of the central government, local governments and communities. The Government of Indonesia is committed to creating 20 Million Ha of conservation areas by 2020.

Economic empowerment of the community is considered very important to realize a balanced, developed and equitable economic structure; grow and develop the ability of community businesses to become resilient and independent businesses; increase the role of society in regional development, job creation, income equality, economic growth, and the alleviation of people from poverty. The economic empowerment efforts that have been taken are to further empower people's efforts to be more efficient, productive and competitive, namely by creating a conducive business climate and business opportunities as wide as possible. In the framework of community business development, partnership relationships need to be developed in the form of mutually supportive and profitable business relationships between large, medium and small businesses and cooperatives in order to strengthen the economic structure. In understanding development, questions must be directed to what is happening with poverty, unemployment and imbalance. Development has been relinquished on the basis of reducing or eliminating poverty, disparity and unemployment in the context of economic development the country is building (Todaro and Smith, 2003). Community empowerment in addition to being a process of flowing power between the authorities to the controlled also includes strengthening of its institutions. In the framework of national development efforts, community empowerment development efforts can be seen from several points of view. First, the creation of an atmosphere or climate that allows society to develop. Second, improving the ability of the community to build through various funding assistance, training, infrastructure development and facilities both physical and social, and institutional development in the region.

Selayar is a cluster of islands located to the south of Sulawesi Island, consisting of several rather large islands and many small islands. The largest of them is P. Selayar, about 100 km long and the width (widest part) is about 15 km, while the smaller ones are P. Kalautoa, P. Tanah Jampea, P. Bonerate, P. Kajuadi, P. Kalao Toa, P. Rajuni, Tambolongan, Polassi and others. Geographically Selayar is a track area, a link between the western and eastern parts of Indonesia. Traders from the western tip of Indonesia, Sumatra, Java who want to find spices and other produce in Maluku and Irian certainly have to go through the Selayar sea route and its surroundings. Similarly, the People of Maluku and Irian who will market their regional products both produce such as copra and spices and marine products such as sea cucumbers and shark fins of course through the sea around Selayar. Selayar Islands Regency is one of the

districts in South Sulawesi Province located between 5°42' - 7°35' South Latitude and 120°15' - 122°30' East Longitude bordering Bulukumba Regency to the North, East Flores Sea, Flores Sea and Makassar Strait to the West and East Nusa Tenggara Province to the South. The area of Selayar Regency is recorded at 1,357.03 km² which includes 11 sub-districts and 75 villages / villages. The potential of the district's marine resources is very large, so far it has not been managed properly so that there are still many residents in Selayar who live below the poverty line. Based on statistical data, the number of poor households in 2009 reached 7,889, so there were about 31,556 people (25.9 percent) of all residents in Selayar Islands Regency (BPS, 2010).

Coastal communities are identical to individuals who live in areas around the coast that are sometimes forgotten by economic development because government policies are mostly only focused on the development of agricultural and land areas, especially in the country, especially for Indonesia as the largest archipelago in the world which has 17,508 islands with a coastline length of 81,000 km, has the potential for very large coastal and ocean resources. The area of Indonesian waters is a large area of 5.8 million km consisting of 3.1 million km². W. Coastal communities are a group of residents living in coastal areas who live together and meet their living needs from resources in coastal areas. Similarly, types of livelihoods that utilize natural resources or environmental services in coastal areas such as fishermen, fish farmers, and owners or workers of the maritime industry. Coastal communities dominated by fisheries businesses in general are still on the poverty line, they have no choice of livelihood, have a low level of education, do not know and realize the preservation of natural resources and the environment. Coastal areas as land areas bordering the sea, the boundaries on land include areas that are inundated with water or not.

A. Problem Formulation

- What is the condition of the coastal communities of Selayar regency?
- How is the economic empowerment strategy of coastal communities based on the local potential of Selayar regency?
- What are the factors that affect the economic empowerment of coastal communities in Selayar district?

II. LIBRARY REVIEW

A. Theory Review

a) Community Economic Empowerment

Understanding Economic Empowerment of Community Empowerment in the Great Dictionary of Indonesian as a noun (noun) which means process, way, deed, empowering (Ministry of National Education, 2008; 300). Empowerment in English is referred to as empowerment. The term empowerment is interpreted as an effort to actualize the potential that people already have in order to become a system that can organize themselves independently. Individuals are not as objects, but as actors who are able to direct themselves in a better direction.

Empowerment is an effort that builds community power by encouraging, motivating and raising awareness of its potential and strives to develop it. Empowerment is directed to improve the economy of the community productively so as to produce high added value and greater income. Efforts to increase the ability to generate added value must at least be improved access to four things, namely access to resources, access to technology, access to markets and access to demand. Community empowerment is an effort to create or increase the capacity of the community, both individually and in groups in solving various problems related to efforts to improve the quality of life, independence and well-being. To develop the economic empowerment of the community, it is necessary to strengthen the ownership of production factors, strengthen the mastery of distribution and marketing. In this context, economic empowerment to strengthen society in obtaining adequate salaries / wages, to obtain information, knowledge and skills, so as to obtain improved results economically. Empowerment in the field of economics is an effort to build power (society) by encouraging, motivating, and raising awareness of its economic potential and strive to develop it. The power of society is the basic element that allows a society to survive. In a dynamic sense, that is, developing oneself and achieving progress. In terms of economic empowerment of the community means all economic activities and efforts of the community to meet the needs of life (basic need) namely clothing, food, boards, health and education. Community economic empowerment used to meet the educational needs of family members is a form of community potential that is used to participate in education. Based on some of the above opinions, community economic empowerment is strengthening the ownership of factors of production, strengthening the mastery of distribution and marketing, strengthening the community to get adequate salaries / wages, and strengthening the community to obtain information, knowledge and skills to improve people's ability to stand alone to overcome their own problems, improve the quality of life, achieve prosperity and improve their lives. his position in society.

B. Understanding coastal communities

Society is a group of relatively independent human beings who live together for a long period of time, inhabiting a region. Certainly by having the same culture, and most of the activities in that group (Paul B. Horton 2015). While According to (Karl Marx, 2015) says in society is a sturktur experiencing organizational tension and development due to the existence of conflict between economically divided groups.

According to Maclver J.L Gilin and J.P Gilin, (M. Munandar Soelaeman's book entitled Basic Social Sciences: Theories and Concepts of Social Sciences) suggests that society is a mutual interaction and interaction is values,

norms and procedures that are a common need so that society is the unity of life.

human beings who interact according to a certain system of customs, which are continuous and bound by a sense of shared identity. People who live, grow, and develop in coastal areas, which is a transitional area between land and sea areas. As a system, fishing societies consist of social categories that form social unity. They also have a value system and symbols culture as a reference to their daily behavior. This cultural factor is a differentiator of the fishing community from other social groups. Most coastal communities, both directly and indirectly, depend on their survival from the potential managers of fishery resources. They become the main components of construction. Indonesian maritime community. According to (Mulyadi 2010), traditional fishermen are the group that suffers the most, poor and often victims of the process marginalization due to fisheries modernization policies. In general, so-called traditional fishermen are fishermen who utilize fishery resources with traditional fishing equipment, small business capital, and relatively simple fishing organizations. In its development, fishermen have been related to dualism in accordance with the development of science and technology so far. People who live from livelihoods, live in coastal or coastal areas, communities of group fishing communities whose livelihoods are from the sea and live in villages or coasts According to Junandar (2010), Household income is the income received by the household concerned both derived from the income of the head of the household and the income of the members of the household. Based on the definition of the above, it can be concluded that household income is income obtained from all members of the family household either from the head of the family or all family members.

C. Empowerment of Coastal Communities

Environmental management in coastal areas the main issue is still very large number of people who are underprivileged (income below the specified average standard) and still have to face health problems, lack of clean water, abrasion, and difficulty achieving a decent level of education, this is because it has not been managed properly. Community empowerment comes from the word "power" that gets.

The prefix that becomes the word "empowered" means to have or have power. Power means strength, power means to have power. The concept of community empowerment includes understanding community development (community development) and development that relies on the community (community-based development). First of all it is necessary to first understand the meaning and meaning of empowerment and empowerment community. Conceptually, empowerment or empowerment (empowerment), derived from the word "power" (strength or power). Community empowerment is a development process where people take the initiative to start the process of social activities to improve their own situation and condition. Functionally, community empowerment is an effort to legitimize and strengthen all forms of existing community movements, community self-welfare movements with the

spearhead of NGOs, community protest movements against the dominance and intervention of the state bureaucracy, the authority of the industrial world, moral movements, which intend to give moral clothes to the naked forces that are the mainstay of social relations and three The last decade community empowerment is an effort to transform the growth of society as a real force of society, to protect and fight for values and interests in the arena of all aspects of life. Community empowerment has the meaning of increasing the ability or increasing community independence, not only including strengthening individuals but also social institutions.

Management of indonesia's coastal and marine resources from a corner View of sustainable development (stainabel development) faced with a position that is not duplicitous, or is at a crossroads. On the one hand, there are several coastal areas that have been utilized (developed) intensively. As a result, indications have exceeded the carrying capacity or sustainable capacity (sustainable potential) of the ecosystem.

Coastal or marine, such as pollution, overfishing, physical degradation of coastal habitats, and coastal abrasion, have appeared in the most important coastal areas. This phenomenon has been and still is ongoing, especially in densely populated coastal areas, and high windows of its development, such as the Strait of Malacca, the North Coast of Java, Bali, and South Sulawesi.

• Types of qualitative research through phenomenological approaches

III. DISCUSSION

A. Condition of Selayar Regency Coastal Communities

The role of coastal communities towards economic improvement since the beginning of human civilization, society both individually and in groups, has an important role in the economy. The economic well-being achieved by society is the result of the collective work of all components in that society. Basically, the role of this community reflects their concern for sasama. They work not always for their own sake, but also for the benefit of others, such as family, relatives, and the surrounding community. There are various motivations about why someone relan "sacrifice" for the benefit of others or It is called altruism, although tanpa gets rewards or benefits directly. The government needs to find an appropriate approach and be outlined in a concept that is able to improve the economy of rural communities. The approach of economic development that reaches from the countryside, by combining the culture of existing communities in rural areas, good habits, which we need to pack back combined with economic concepts that are easily understood by the community.

The management of indonesia's coastal and marine resources from the point of view of sustainable development (stainabel development) is faced with a position that is not duplicitous, or is at a crossroads. On the one hand, there are several coastal areas that have been utilized (developed) intensively. As a result, indications of overstayment of the carrying capacity or sustainable capacity (sustainable

potential) of coastal or marine ecosystems, such as pollution, overfishing, physical degradation of coastal habitats, and coastal abrasion, have emerged in the most important coastal areas. This phenomenon has been and still is ongoing, especially in densely populated coastal areas, and high windows of its development, such as the Strait of Malacca, the North Coast of Java, Bali, and South Sulawesi.

Selayar Regency community is the active participation and full support of all stakeholders whose source of life directly depends on marine products. The main argument in formulating this strategy plan, based on the fact that Selayar Regency has considerable coastal and marine resources. One of the keys to success in the economic empowerment of the people of Selayar Islands Regency is the active participation and full support of all stakeholders whose livelihoods directly depend on marine products. The production of fishing communities in Selayar Islands Regency is very dependent on the weather. In certain seasons, the amount of bias production is abundant to the point that it cannot be absorbed by the market. This causes prices to be very low due to abundant harvests. But when the dry season or bad weather, production is so small that the results of going to sea are not able to cover operational costs.

B. Economic Empowerment Strategy

Patterns of Community Economic Empowerment In an effort to improve people's living standards, the right empowerment pattern is needed. The right form of empowerment is to provide opportunities for the poor to plan and implement the development programs they have determined. Some forms of community economic empowerment practices are:

- Capital Assistance. One aspect of the problem faced by the power tuna community is capital. The slow accumulation of capital among micro, small, and medium enterprises, is one of the causes of the slow pace of business development and the low business surplus in the micro, small and medium enterprise sectors. community empowerment efforts in the economic field through this aspect of capital are 1) the provision of capital assistance does not cause community dependence; (2) the breakdown of this aspect of capital is carried out through the creation of a new conducive system for micro enterprises, small businesses, and medium enterprises to gain access in financial institutions.
- Business encourages productivity and business growth, will not have any significance for the community, if the production cannot be marketed, or can be sold only at a very low price. Therefore, an important component in the effort to empower people in the economic field is the development of production and marketing infrastructure. The availability of marketing infrastructure and/or transportation from production sites to markets, will reduce the marketing chain and will ultimately increase the acceptance of farmers and micro-entrepreneurs, small entrepreneurs, and medium-sized entrepreneurs. That is, in terms of economic empowerment, the project to build infrastructure supporting the village is lagging behind, it is strategic.
- Assistance Assistance. The assistance of the deaf community is necessary and important. The main task of

this assistance is to facilitate the learning process or reflection and to be a mediator for strengthening partnerships between micro-businesses, small businesses, as well as medium-sized businesses with large businesses.

- Institutional strengthening of economic empowerment in weak communities, initially carried out through an individual approach. This individual approach does not give satisfactory results. Therefore, the approach taken should be with a group approach. The reason is, the accumulation of capital will be difficult to achieve among the poor, therefore the accumulation of capital must be done together in a group container or joint effort. Similarly, with the problem of distribution, the poor cannot control the distribution of production output and production inputs, individually. Through groups, they can build strength to help determine distribution.
- Strengthening business partnerships. Community empowerment in the economic field is mutual strengthening, where the big will only develop if there are small and medium, and small will develop if there are large and medium. High competitiveness exists only if there is a link between the big and the medium and small. Because only with a fair production linkage, efficiency will be built. Therefore, through partnerships in the field of capital, partnerships in the production process, partnerships in distribution, each party will be empowered.

According to the author, the economic empowerment of the community that occurs individually needs to be supported by the local government both in policy and assistance support to facilitate the sustainable development of community efforts. Besides

In addition, other forms of government support can be in the form of increasing the poor's understanding of business development through credit assistance or forms of assistance in improving community skills.

C. Factors Affecting Economic Empowerment

In general, the issue of coastal community income is used as a benchmark for the success, prosperity and economic progress of a community. But this measure is not the only measuring instrument, but also used other benchmarks, such as the level of employment opportunities, employment, price level, sales volume, and so on. In addition, income (money) is also called "income" which is the reward received by all households at the level of society in a country / region, from the delivery of factors of production or after carrying out economic activities. The income is used by the community to meet the needs of consumers and the rest is savings (savings) to meet the future. In empowerment there are conditions where society in general has similar rights and obligations that are realized in opportunities, positions, roles based on attitudes and behaviors that help each other in all aspects of people's lives. Empowerment efforts require support from sharing parties, both government and nongovernmental organizations. The empowerment carried out has the impact of community empowerment to get out of structural barriers, so that this empowered society can later actualize its potential and capacity to face external challenges as a result of building.

Human quality as an object of human resource development with two indicators, namely instrumental indicators and substantial indicators. Instrumental indicators include creativity, freedom, responsibility and productive ability. Substantial indicators include social, political, religious, economic, cultural, scientific and physical aspects. Both can be used to see the success of human quality development. Substantially, the successful development of human qualities is demonstrated in the form of income, education, health, faith, physical toughness, mental toughness, and art. Empowerment in the economy is formed as the antithesis to the development model and industrialization model that is less favorable to the majority people.

This concept is built from the following logical framework:

- That the process of concentrating power is awakened from the concentration of mastery of production factors.
- The concentration of production factor power will give birth to working people and communities that are fringe entrepreneurs.
- Power will build a manipulative upper building or knowledge system, political system, legal system, and ideology to strengthen and legitimacy.
- Co-opting knowledge systems, legal systems, political systems, and ideologies will systematically create two groups of people, namely empowered communities and deaf people. Finally what happens is a dichotomy, that is, a ruling society and a controlled human being. To free the situation of mastering and mastering, it must be released through the empowerment process for the mastered. Therefore, the ultimate goal of community empowerment in the economic field is to increase the income of weak people. People's income in general comes from wages / salaries and from business surpluses. In general, people who are economically disabled (not capable) only receive low wages/ salaries. The low salary / wages received by the deaf community is due to them generally have limited skills.

In general, strategy priorities and program elaboration of all components in the SWOT factors that have been identified, strategy programs based on the generating results of the SWOT matrix are as follows:

- SO (strength-opportunity) strategies include a more intensive credit facility socialization program for fishermen and a market intervention program (opening market opportunities) by the government,
- WO strategy (weakness-opportunity) includes programs to introduce appropriate technology to fishermen, and development programs for diversifying fish processing businesses;
- ST strategy (threat-strength includes marine security suppression program by security forces, and deregulation program for distribution of fuel oil (BBM) specifically for fishermen;
- WT strategy (weakness-threat) includes material price subsidy program fuel oil (BBM) for fishermen and regulatory programs to prevent de-rationing through customary rules.

The results of the SWOT analysis showed that the strength component (S) had the highest weight value in determining the empowerment strategy of the fishing community, followed by the opportunity component (O), weakness (W), and threat (T). The internal factors of the fishing community empowerment strategy are dominated by the strength component, while the dominant external factor is the threat component. The magnitude of strength and threat factors compared to weaknesses and opportunities in the strategy of empowering fishing communities is an indicator of success in the empowerment of fishing communities in Selayar Islands Regency. Furthermore, from the strengths component, the decisive factors in the empowerment strategy of the fishing community of Selayar Islands Regency are:

- high family spirit;
- high morale;
- tough in the face of life's difficulties.

Based on the results of the analysis of these strength factors, it turns out that the high morale factor is the main strength factor in the empowerment strategy of the fishing community of Selayar Islands Regency. High morale in managing the potential of aquatic resources is the main capital that has the potential to be developed. Thus, this factor is expected to be maximized, seeing the breadth of potential available for improving the welfare of the fishing community of Selayar Islands Regency in the future. To date.

It is proven that the Selayar Islands Regency area is an archipelago area consisting mostly of sea waters. In addition, high morale and rigidity in the face of life difficulties from fishermen is a strength factor that is also important to note, because it is the carrying capacity of the main force factor in improving the welfare of the fishing community of Selayar Islands Regency. The results of the analysis of the weakness component of the decisive factors in the community empowerment strategy of Selayar Regency are

- skills and mastery of technology are still lacking;
- the entrepreneurial soul is easy;
- low average education level;
- bargaining positions against low steamers traders.

For this reason, the formulation of strategies that will be implemented in the empowerment of fishing communities needs to consider this factor in order to run in accordance with what is desired. The results of the analysis of the opportunity component or opportunities, the factors that determine in the strategy of empowering the fishing community of Selayar Islands Regency are: 1

- high demand for fish production;
- the availability of credit facilities for fishermen;
- fishing ground locations are close and wide;
- Cheap labor
- The quality of the waters is quite good.

Based on the results of the ranking analysis of the above opportunity factors, it is known that the cheap labor factor is the most important factor to be optimized, as an opportunity for empowerment of selayar regency fishing

communities. It is also supported by a fishing ground location (fishing ground) that is close and wide is quite an important opportunity to be considered. Based on the results of the data processing above, it shows that the lowest-weight SWOT component is the opportunity component. Components of threats factors that determine the strategy institutional development of community food barns are:

- damage to marine ecosystems due to destructive capture;
- the market price is determined by the collecting party;
- high fuel prices;
- Fishing depending on the season
- Production results fluctuate.

Based on the results of the ranking analysis of these threat factors, Damage to marine ecosystems due to destructive capture is a serious threat factor in the empowerment of fishing communities in Selayar Islands Regency. The weight of this factor is very high this indicates that this factor is expected to be overcome soon and it is expected that there is a strategy that will be implemented to be able to immediately overcome the problem. In general, of all the SWOT factors that have been identified, the highest priority factor is in the empowerment strategy of the fishing community. In improving the welfare of the fishing community of Selayar Regency in a row are:

- increased productivity of fishermen;
- increased role of local institutions
- Conservation of fish resources.

The results of the SWOT analysis showed that the component of increasing fishermen's productivity had the highest weight value in the selection of alternative fishing community empowerment programs in Selayar Regency, followed by the component of increasing the role of local institutions.

IV. CONCLUSION

Selayar Regency as a new district experienced relatively high productive age population growth, where the population mostly settled in rural and coastal areas. People depend their lives around the fisheries sector. People in Selayar Regency have an interest and entrepreneurial spirit that is driven by the needs and the higher cost of living. Interest and entrepreneurial spirit is shown by community participation in small and medium-sized micro enterprise activities.

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